

INDIA-SRI LANKA RELATIONS AND CHINESE INVESTMENTS IN SRI LANKA

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ABSTRACT

China's broad Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) has led to more Chinese investment throughout Asia, notably in Sri Lanka. These investments have recently received criticism, due to rising geopolitical rivalry in the Indian Ocean and also Sri Lanka's strategic position and ports in the area. Geostrategic threats are fueling fears that Beijing will be using ports and other projects for military objectives. Sri Lanka has been a significant political and economic partner for China. Due to its geographical location as a hub of the projected 21st-Century Maritime Silk Road, Sri Lanka has now become a new investment hot zone since Chinese President Xi Jinping launched the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) in 2013. There are concerns that by allowing Beijing's investment, Sri Lanka risks becoming trapped in a debt trap, with both legal and illicit Chinese labour displacing local workers.

Keywords: *BRI, Debt Trap, Economic Diplomacy, String of Pearls*

Introduction

Sri Lanka appears to have established stronger commercial, military, and diplomatic ties with China in recent years. Sri Lanka, for example, has invited Chinese investment in the building of a port in Hambantota, has acquired Chinese weaponry for use in its civil war, and has been designated as a "dialogue partner" by the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO). Analysts concerned about the increase of Chinese presence elsewhere in the Indian Ocean region (IOR), such as in Gwadar, Pakistan, and Kyaukpyu, Myanmar, have been alarmed by such high-profile movements.

In India-Sri Lanka relations, China has emerged as a significant player. Before looking deeper into the various facets of China's footprints in Sri Lanka and their effect on India-Sri Lanka relations, it's necessary to put this intervening element into perspective. China's policy against India, according to Mohan Malik, has three elements: encirclement, envelopment, and entanglement. The term 'Encirclement' refers to a strengthened Chinese military presence [encircling India] in Tibet, Pakistan, Nepal, Sri Lanka,

Bangladesh, Burma, and the Indian Ocean island states. The term 'Envelopment' refers to the process of integrating all of India's neighbours into the Chinese economy, and 'Entanglement' is taking advantage of India's internal inconsistencies and various security issues.

India is not alarmed by China's footprint, but it is concerned about the geopolitical consequences. The biggest source of worry is the risk of Chinese infrastructure being used against Indian interests. In the Annexure to the India-Sri Lanka Accord of 1987, India and Sri Lanka concluded that "Trincomalee or any other port in Sri Lanka would not be made available to any country for military use in a manner prejudicial to India's interest." India believes that Colombo will take this clause seriously. However, caution is advised considering Sri Lanka's failure to completely implement even the key provisions of the Accord, citing numerous reasons and justifications. It would not take long to violate this clause in the Annexure. The prospect of the dual-use mode of such infrastructure projects is a source of concern for India. For example, China is permitted to provide storage and fueling facilities at Hambantota, despite

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the fact that India has been given the same facilities. Similarly, with Chinese assistance, the Colombo Port, which handles roughly 70% of India's shipping, is modernized with the help of China. If China so desires, it can still turn these ventures against India in a confrontation scenario. New Delhi has taken a number of measures to resolve these issues. In a similar case in the 1980s, India was forceful in expressing its point of view. Via the bilateral Accord of July 1987, it ensured that Sri Lanka was not used by powers hostile to India's interests. However, in the current sense, India has dealt with the topic more subtly.

China's Investments in Colombo and Hambantota

Infrastructure development with wider strategic implications is the main Chinese footprint in Sri Lanka that has triggered India's interest. China has built significant infrastructure projects in the island state, including the Hambantota port, the Katunayake-Colombo Expressway, the Norochcholai Coal Power Plant, Maththala Airport, the Colombo South Harbour Expansion Project, a 661-room Shangri La hotel, and the Colombo Center for Performing Arts. According to statistics, China funds more than half of Sri Lanka's construction and development loans. The most discussed project is the Hambantota port. The first phase of the port was completed in 2010 at a cost of \$360 million by China Harbour Engineering Co. Ltd. It has a high-quality passenger terminal as well as freight storage, warehousing, bunkering, provisioning, servicing and repair, medical supplies, and customs clearance facilities. Colombo attempts to project the notion that the Chinese presence in the Hambantota port is solely commercial. The harbour, however, is strategically positioned not only for Beijing's merchant vessels and cargo ships travelling to or from Africa and the Middle East to make a stay but it can also be utilized by any naval ship.

A heavy Chinese presence in Hambantota will give them control over a large region of the Indian Ocean stretching from Australia in the East to Africa in the west and up to Antarctica in the south. It may not be challenging for China to keep a close eye on all ships – military and non-military – that travel between India's east and west coasts, encircling Sri Lanka. Ironically, Colombo had suggested a joint venture with India to develop the

Hambantota port, but China seized the opportunity when the talks were still ongoing. According to Sri Lanka, 'China bid the best terms' and 'we don't have favourites'. India's decision-making response time should be improved.

In terms of infrastructure growth, India's presence in Sri Lanka is minimal, if not non-existent, in contrast to China. However, Sri Lankans score the Chinese higher in terms of project completion time, cost-effectiveness, and infrastructure efficiency. Most notably, Beijing attaches no provisions to their loans in terms of "structural changes, policy revisions, fair bidding, or transparency," or even human rights, other than taking in some of their own labourers. When opposed to their Chinese rivals, Indian firms have certain underlying drawbacks. While most Indian firms are privately held, Chinese firms are state-owned and backed by state financial institutions such as China Development Bank Corporation, Industrial and Commercial Bank of China (ICBC), etc. For Chinese businesses, profit comes second. Their top priority is to consider factors such as geographical benefits, diplomatic mileage, and goodwill earned through programs. Most notably, in the Indian situation, the private and public sectors do not seem to balance each other's activities and benefits. Without much state patronage and inspiration, risk-averse Indian firms care less about projecting Indian soft power. This argument should be considered by the Indian government in its economic diplomacy.

Sri Lanka is not the only country where China is becoming more visible. Apart from Sri Lanka, Beijing has long-established maritime and other links with countries in eastern Africa, Seychelles, Mauritius, West Asia, Pakistan, Maldives, Bangladesh, Myanmar, and Southeast Asian countries. The key goal is to ensure the protection of its sea lanes, especially the uninterrupted flow of vital energy supplies from Africa and West Asia. At the same time, these associations have served as a virtual encirclement of India, which some analysts refer to as the 'String of Pearls' construction.

The China Communications Construction Company is funding the Colombo Port City Initiative, which is a large-scale land reclamation project (CCCC). Via the building of the Colombo Port City, both countries intend to foster economic

growth and infrastructure upgrade in Sri Lanka's western metropolitan area as a flagship project of the Mahinda Vision and the MSR. The CCCC and the Sri Lanka Investment Authority concluded a port city investment agreement in Colombo in November 2013. According to the deal, China Harbor Engineering Co., Ltd. (CHEC), a wholly-owned subsidiary of the CCCC, is in charge of the land's initial production. The first phase expected to last three years and will require an investment of \$1.4 billion; the second phase will require an investment of more than \$13 billion. The project will reclaim 276 hectares of coastal land and add over 5 million square meters of building space, on which will be constructed a high-end urban development project combining industrial, industry, financial, tourism, and residential functions.

The Colombo Port City Project was declared a 'calamity' on March 4, 2015, and was suspended by the new government on the grounds that its environmental effect needs to be reassessed and that appropriate inspection and approval procedures were missing. In the following year, top Sri Lankan officials traveled regularly between countries such as India, Japan, and the United States, finding new sources of loans and investments to cover financial and infrastructure deficits to address its economy's immediate needs, but these attempts fell short. However, reports indicate that the project's suspension was mostly due to political strife in Sri Lanka. About the fact that Sirsena suspended the scheme, he and other top officials were cited on several occasions as saying that the current situation with regard to the project is transient and short-lived and that the concern is not with China.

Hambantota is about 240 kilometres southeast of Colombo and has a population of over 500,000 people. The natives depend primarily on fishing and farming for a living, making it one of the country's most economically backward and low-income regions. Many years back, the Sri Lankan central government debated and conducted studies on a proposal to establish an international port in Hambantota. However, the protracted civil war slowed its growth, and the proposal to modernize the port was eventually abandoned. After Rajapaksa was elected president in 2005, the construction of the Hambantota port was resurrected. During the final years of the civil war, the Sri Lankan government

requested foreign aid from a variety of sources. However, no single nation expressed an interest in building the port city. The first phase of the Hambantota Development Agreement was agreed in 2007 by CHEC and the Sri Lankan Port Authority. The contract's first phase covers two 100,000-ton container terminals, a 100,000-ton tanker terminal, a 420,000-square-meter yard, and other port infrastructure and operational equipment. The second phase of the project entails building four 100,000 DWT container berths, one 100,000-ton port, two 30,000-ton berths, one offshore artificial island, and 400,000 square meters of road yard. When completed, the port will have more than thirty berths, making it the largest in South Asia.

The port's supporting infrastructure includes a 500-hectare international airport expansion, a 25-kilometre expressway stretch from the airport to downtown Hambantota, and a 50-square-kilometre industrial park. With the integration of harbours, industrial parks, and towns, this region will eventually become a 'locomotive' that drives Sri Lanka's economic development. The industrial park will provide transportation facilities, logistics, seafood manufacturing, agricultural, and sideline commodity processing in order to support industrial upgrading in Sri Lanka. It is planned to generate about 100,000 jobs and about \$5 billion in investment. After upgrading its infrastructure, Hambantota port has the capacity to challenge Singapore's Asian shipping centre status. The debate over the construction of the Hambantota port region represents the complexities of China's approach to development beyond its boundaries. China views its own policy experience of state-led infrastructure development as a successful way to achieve fast economic growth. However, considering the expense and size of investment ventures like Hambantota, China has found its projects and motivations for international economic cooperation in the spotlight amid elections and other political outlets.

India-Sri Lanka Relations: Beijing as a Factor

The relationship between India and Sri Lanka had deteriorated gradually under Rajapaksa due to frequent diplomatic miscalculations by both countries. Sirisena said in his election manifesto that Sri Lanka will not be anti-India or reliant on India. At his official opening, he said that his foreign policy would mend relations with the international

community. Sirisena made a point of visiting India first since becoming President, indicating that good ties with Delhi were a priority. Four agreements were concluded between the two nations. The first was a historic treaty on nuclear security, which Sri Lanka concluded with every nation. The Rajapaksa regime regarded the Kudankulam nuclear plant in Tamil Nadu as a "threat" due to the possibility of an accident. Sirisena acknowledged India's assurance of protection in the event of an accident. Others included commerce, agricultural partnership in various fields, and cultural and educational cooperation.

Mr Modi became the first Indian Prime Minister since July 1987 to visit Sri Lanka. He agreed to counter the trade deficit, including an extra \$318 million for Sri Lankan railways, and raise the swap arrangement to stabilize Sri Lanka's currency in the event of a crisis from \$400 million to \$1.5 billion. Aware of Sri Lanka's internal Tamil crisis, he said that he is a "firm believer in cooperative federalism" and assured the Sri Lankan Parliament that "unity and integrity of Sri Lanka are paramount" for India. It's in our best interests." The arrangement between India and Sri Lanka to jointly construct petroleum storage facilities in the eastern port city of Trincomalee could be strategically significant in the future. Indian Prime Minister Mr Modi said that India would "assist Trincomalee in becoming a regional petroleum hub." This might eventually contribute to strategic access to this port, offsetting China's access to Hambantota. Modi also promised to develop a Buddhist circuit in India and requested Sri Lanka help to create a Ramayana Trail. The two countries agreed to continue with talks to solve the Indian concern of fishing rights at Palk Strait.

Sri Lanka is not a major exporting or importing partner for China in terms of total bilateral trade volume. But, China became Sri Lanka's second-largest importing country in 2008 – up from the third place in 2007, Although India continues to be the top source of imports to Sri Lanka, trade between China and Sri Lanka has become more robust in recent years. Looking at data from both the Sri Lankan and Chinese governments shows this. It is worth noting that, amid the recent rise in Sri Lankan trade with China, trade with its northern neighbour, India, has been growing at a faster pace.

Conclusion

What is more necessary is to effectively leverage the factor of proximity. New Delhi should actively create constituencies in the surrounding area and engage in conversation with the relevant political, economic, social, and cultural actors. If there are some concerns about China's position in the region, there is nothing wrong with dealing with the problem bilaterally with China. India must strike a balance between regional stability, its own strategic interests, long-term security, and Sri Lanka's growth. The key is to maintain long-term bilateral relations with Sri Lanka and make up for lost ground. When it comes to its development position in a third world, New Delhi must consider its own strengths and limitations. It should aspire to have a competitive advantage in whatever areas it can. Resettlement, tourism, cultural exchange, and commerce are few places that India has a distinct advantage over other countries.

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